

The marginal energy and water cost of AI inference

Ivann Puslecki¹ and Joseph Morlier²

¹ ivann.puslecki@universite-paris-saclay-alumni.eu, Ile de France, France

² Université de Toulouse, ISAE-SUPAERO, Toulouse, France

Abstract

Public debate frequently portrays artificial intelligence inference as highly energy- and water-intensive, often based on opaque or inconsistent assumptions. In this paper, we provide a bottom-up estimation of the marginal electricity and water footprint of large language model inference using top level hypothesis. Using explicit computational, hardware, and infrastructure parameters, we demonstrate that a single query typically consumes around 1.3 Wh of electricity and 4.3 milliliters of water. These estimates suggest that marginal impacts may be lower than previously estimated through top-down attribution methods.

Figure 1: Marginal energy and water cost of AI inference illustrated in one scheme.

Large language models (LLMs) have prompted renewed scrutiny of the environmental footprint of artificial intelligence. Prior work has extensively quantified the energy and carbon cost of model training [1, 2], and has explored mitigation strategies including hardware efficiency improvements and model compression [3]. By contrast, the environmental cost of inference, the operational phase corresponding to user queries-remains comparatively less rigorously characterized and is frequently discussed using coarse averages or speculative extrapolations [4].

Mainstream media typically confound marginal and average costs, mix training and inference, or rely on outdated hardware assumptions. To clarify these facts and provide a reliable estimate, we adopt a bottom-up formulation linking token generation to floating-point operations (FLOPs), execution time, and electricity consumption.

Scenario	T_{total} (tokens)	FLOPs per query (F)
Low usage	500	2.0×10^{14}
Average usage	1300	5.2×10^{14}
High usage	4100	2.14×10^{15}

Table 1: Summary of computational load across representative inference scenarios. FLOPs are calculated assuming 2×10^{11} active parameters per token (Eq. (1)).

For representative cloud-scale inference using 2×10^{11} active parameters [5], the marginal electricity consumption per query is estimated at 0.5 – 5.6 Wh across typical prompt lengths of approximately 500 – 4100 tokens. Uncertainty propagation accounting for token variability, hardware utilization, and server power draw yields relative uncertainties of the order of tens of percent.

These estimates are systematically lower than several previously reported values, as they reflect the marginal energetic cost of executing a single query on already-provisioned hardware. By contrast, approaches that allocate total facility energy across an assumed query volume conflate marginal inference costs with average service intensity, thereby incorporating contributions from idle capacity, ancillary background processes, and, in some cases, amortized training energy.

The manufacturing of computer equipment generates energy that must be amortized over the lifetime of its use. Using manufacturer-reported cradle-to-gate carbon data for H100-class systems [6] and converting to energy via regional electricity emission factors [7], we can then obtain an upper-bound embodied energy of order 5×10^2 kWh per accelerator. Amortized over a multi-year operational lifetime at moderate utilization, this contributes $\ll 0.05$ Wh per query, typically a small correction to operational electricity at the per query scale, though material at global deployment scale.

Electricity consumption translates into water use through both direct data center cooling (Scope 1) and upstream electricity generation (Scope 2), with additional amortized manufacturing impacts (Scope 3). Using representative water-use effectiveness (WUE) and US-average water intensity factors [8, 9], the total per-query water consumption is estimated at a few milliliters ($\sim 1.7 - 19.3$ mL), with a representative average of 43mL. Scope 2 contributions dominate the budget, while Scope 3 impacts become negligible when amortized over the operational lifetime throughput of the hardware. However, these values are highly sensitive to geographical context: the regional electricity mix and local climate strongly modulate water intensity, meaning that identical computational tasks may yield significantly different water footprints depending on the grid’s generation profile.

On the scale of an individual interaction, an average query that consumes ~ 1.3 Wh corresponds to operating a 10 W LED bulb for several minutes or a laptop for roughly one minute [10]. The associated water footprint is orders of magnitude below the ones from common food products [11]. These comparisons are not intended to trivialize cumulative impacts. At billions of queries per day, the aggregate electricity demand becomes substantial and can contribute measurably to regional grid loads [12, 13]. *The essential distinction here lies between the marginal intensity per request and scale effects at the system level.*

Environmental scrutiny of the AI infrastructure remains warranted. Data centers increasingly report substantial water withdrawals, particularly in water-stressed regions [14]. Growth trajectories suggest that absolute impacts will be governed by deployment scale, hardware efficiency gains, grid decarbonization, and cooling design choices. **Crucially, these gains in marginal efficiency may be offset by a rebound effect, where reduced costs per inference drive an expansion in total demand that sustains or even increases aggregate resource consumption.** Therefore, transparent system boundary definitions and explicit parameterization of key variables are essential

for more reliable impact assessment [15].

Methods

Inference in transformer-based LLMs is autoregressive: tokens are generated sequentially. The total computational cost F scales approximately with the number of active parameters N and the total token count $T_{\text{total}} = T_{\text{in}} + T_{\text{out}}$. We assume two FLOPs per parameter per token, corresponding to a multiply-accumulate operation [16, 17] as expressed in Eq. (1):

$$F \approx 2NT_{\text{total}} \quad (1)$$

For our estimates, we assume $N \sim 2 \times 10^{11}$ active parameters and token volumes spanning short to long interactions (hundreds to a few thousand tokens). To translate computation into electricity, we define maximum accelerator throughput Φ_{peak} , utilization η , server power draw P_{server} , and data-center power usage effectiveness (PUE). Execution time t and facility-level electricity per query E_{query} are calculated as Eq. 3:

$$t = \frac{F}{\eta\Phi_{\text{peak}}} \quad (2)$$

$$E_{\text{query}} = P_{\text{server}}t \times \text{PUE} \quad (3)$$

The combined formulation used for our upper-bound estimates is Eq. 4 where the factor 3.6×10^3 converts joules to watt-hours ($1 \text{ Wh} = 3600 \text{ J}$):

$$E_{\text{query(Wh)}} = \frac{1}{3600} \times P_{\text{server}} \frac{2NT_{\text{total}}}{\eta\Phi_{\text{peak}}} \times \text{PUE} \quad (4)$$

Parameter ranges are chosen conservatively to provide upper-bound order-of-magnitude estimates. The active parameter count is set to 2×10^{11} ; token counts span several hundred to several thousand tokens per interaction. Accelerator peak throughput corresponds to FP16 tensor-core performance of current-generation hardware (H100-class) [18]. The utilization η reflects sustained inference conditions and accounts for memory and batching limitations.

Using representative values for contemporary high-end accelerators [18], $\Phi_{\text{peak}} \sim 2 \times 10^{15}$ FLOPs s^{-1} , conservative utilization $\eta \sim 0.1$, server power $\sim 1.5 \text{ kW}$, and PUE ~ 1.18 [8, 19], we obtain marginal electricity consumption on the order of $0.5 - 5.6 \text{ Wh}$ per query.

Embodied energy per accelerator is derived from reported cradle-to-gate carbon emissions [6] converted using regional electricity emission factors [7], and amortized over lifetime operational energy assuming multi-year service and moderate utilization.

The final water footprint is computed as Eq 5:

$$W_{\text{query}} = E_{\text{query}} \times \left(\frac{WUE_{\text{scope1}}}{\text{PUE}} + WUE_{\text{scope2}} + WUE_{\text{scope3}} \right) + E_{\text{emb}} \times WUE_{\text{scope3}}, \quad (5)$$

where water intensities are drawn from published data [8, 9]. Scope 3 water is amortized over lifetime hardware energy.

To bridge the gap between theoretical estimation and empirical observation, we developed SOBRIA, an open-source monitoring framework designed to measure the real-time energy consumption of local AI inference. This tool facilitates the validation of our bottom-up model across various hardware configurations and promotes transparent environmental reporting in AI operations.

Data availability

All parameters are derived from publicly available sources cited in the manuscript. No proprietary datasets were used. The code of SOBRIA is freely available at: <https://github.com/mid2SUPAERO/SOBRIA>

Supplementary Information

S1. Expanded parameter table

Parameter	Value (range)
Active parameters (N)	$2 \times 10^{11} \pm 1 \times 10^{11}$
Total tokens (T_{total})	500–4100
Peak throughput (Φ_{peak})	2×10^{15} FLOPs s ⁻¹
Utilization (η)	0.10 ± 0.02
Server power (P_{server})	1.5 ± 0.3 kW
Power usage effectiveness (PUE)	1.18
Accelerator embodied energy	$\sim 5 \times 10^2$ kWh
Operational lifetime	4 years
Utilization (lifetime average)	60%

S2. FLOP derivation

Transformer inference cost scales approximately as two floating-point operations per parameter per token, reflecting multiply–accumulate operations in linear layers. Attention layers introduce quadratic scaling in sequence length, but for typical conversational contexts the linear parameter term dominates. Total FLOPs per query are therefore approximated as

$$F \approx 2NT_{\text{total}}.$$

This provides an order-of-magnitude upper-bound estimate for dense architectures. Enhancements such as Mixture-of-experts or sparse activation would reduce effective active parameters and therefore FLOPs.

S3. Sensitivity analysis

Electricity consumption scales linearly with:

$$E_{\text{query}} \propto \frac{NT_{\text{total}}P_{\text{server}}}{\eta\Phi_{\text{peak}}}.$$

A twofold increase in utilization reduces per-query electricity by half. A twofold increase in FLOPs-per-watt hardware efficiency similarly halves electricity. The token count is the dominant user-dependent variable.

Relative uncertainty is estimated assuming independent errors:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta E}{E}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\Delta P}{P}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta \eta}{\eta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta T}{T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta N}{N}\right)^2.$$

S4. Embodied energy amortization

Accelerator cradle-to-gate carbon emissions are converted to energy using regional electricity emission factors. The resulting embodied energy per accelerator is $\mathcal{O}(10^2\text{--}10^3)$ kWh.

Assuming four-year service at 60% utilization, the amortized embodied electricity per query remains below 0.05 Wh for typical inference volumes, indicating that operational electricity dominates marginal impact.

S5. Water accounting framework

To bridge the gap between abstract computational metrics and environmental policy, we propose a unified Inference Water Footprint Function (W_{total}). This formula serves as a transparent accounting standard that can be adapted to any model architecture or geographic location :

$$W_{\text{total}} [\text{L}] = E_{\text{query}} \left(\frac{WUE_{\text{scope}1}}{\text{PUE}} + WUE_{\text{scope}2} + WUE_{\text{scope}3} \right) + E_{\text{emb}} \cdot WUE_{\text{scope}3}$$

$$E_{\text{query}} [\text{kWh}] = \frac{P_{\text{server}} [\text{kW}]}{3.6 \times 10^6} \cdot \frac{(T_{\text{in}} + T_{\text{out}}) \cdot 2 \cdot N_{\text{params}}}{\eta \cdot \Phi_{\text{peak}}} \cdot \text{PUE}$$

$$E_{\text{emb}} [\text{kWh}] = \frac{E_{\text{embodied}}^{(\text{upper})} [\text{kWh}]}{N_{\text{queries}}}$$

Where:

- $T_{\text{in}} + T_{\text{out}}$: Total volume of tokens (input and output).
- N_{params} : Number of model active parameters.
- η : Hardware utilization factor.
- Φ_{peak} : Peak floating-point throughput of the accelerator (FLOPs/s).
- P_{server} : Total server power draw.
- **PUE** : Power Usage Effectiveness of the data center.
- $WUE_{\text{scope} i}$: Water usage effectiveness / water intensity for Scope i , applied at its compatible energy boundary (Scope 1 on IT energy; Scopes 2 and 3 on delivered electricity and embodied energy, respectively). To reach our estimate of 4.3 mL for an average query (1.3 Wh), we use the following intensity factors (noting that 1 mL/Wh \equiv 1 L/kWh):
 - $WUE_{\text{scope}1}$ (Direct cooling): 0.3 mL/Wh [8]
 - $WUE_{\text{scope}2}$ (Electricity generation): 3.1 mL/Wh [9]
 - $WUE_{\text{scope}3}$ (Embedded/Manufacturing): 0.016 mL/Wh (amortized)

Regional electricity mix remains the primary driver of $W_{\text{scope}2}$ variability.

- E_{query} : Facility-level electricity consumed during the execution of a single inference query, expressed in watt-hours. Because E_{query} is defined at the facility boundary (i.e. it already incorporates PUE), the Scope 1 water intensity is applied to the IT-level electricity $E_{\text{query}}/\text{PUE}$, while Scope 2 and Scope 3 intensities are applied to the full facility-level value.
- $E_{\text{embodied}}^{(\text{upper})}$: Upper-bound estimate of the embodied energy associated with manufacturing and deploying a single H100 accelerator, expressed in watt-hours.
- N_{queries} : Lifetime inference volume of the server, defined as the ratio between total operational energy consumed over the server lifetime and the operational energy required to execute a single inference query.

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